

FEATURES OF PROFESSIONAL SELF-DETERMINATION OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF STUDYING AT A UNIVERSITY

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***Abstract.** The paper analyzes the features of professional self-determination of students in the process of studying at the university, and also develops practical recommendations for improving the effectiveness of the university's activities in the development of professional self-determination of students.*

***Keywords:** professional self-determination, motivational training, personality.*

For many decades, the attention of researchers has been drawn to the problems of self-determination. Self-determination refers to the "ability of people to live their lives as they choose, in accordance with their own values, preferences, and abilities." Self-determination plays an important role in the developmental outcomes of learners. For example, self-determination contributes to employment and a higher level of quality of life and life satisfaction [1].

Professional self-determination of students is a complex and multifaceted process that includes the awareness of personal abilities and preferences, active exploration of various fields of activity, analysis of the information received, and its comparison with their own expectations and goals. Students resort to various methods and sources of information, including online resources, literature, internships, and interviews, to gain a more complete understanding of possible professional paths. However, the process of self-determination does not always proceed smoothly, and students may face difficulties and uncertainty. Despite this, overcoming these difficulties contributes to a deep understanding of oneself and one's professional goals [3].

In the context of the rapid development of technologies that are changing the demands of the labor market, students need to have a clear understanding of their professional goals and the ways to achieve them. Successful professional self-determination contributes not only to personal growth and satisfaction in professional activities but also to increasing the competitiveness of graduates in the labor market; in this regard, we have developed practical recommendations that will help universities optimize their educational programs by adapting them to the needs of the modern student. The implementation of practical tools, such as career guidance courses, master classes on the development of personal growth and professional development skills, as well as internship and practical training programs in leading companies, contributes to the formation in students of a realistic idea of the labor sphere and their own capabilities. An important aspect of such work is also taking into account the individual characteristics of each student. Personalized approaches to the development of professional self-determination, based on the analysis of the interests, skills, and goals of each student, make it possible to use the university's resources as efficiently as possible and achieve optimal results.

In general, the work on improving the efficiency of the university's activities in the development of professional self-determination of students not only meets the modern

requirements of the educational environment but also contributes to the formation of a competitive and self-confident specialist capable of successful self-realization in modern society.

In this regard, a motivational training program for students was developed.

The main task of the motivational training is the actualization of the psychological resources of the student's personality and the stimulation to develop sustainable educational and professional motivation, as well as the determination of factors and conditions that contribute to the transfer of mental neo-formations acquired in the training and the experience of managing one's own motivation into the professional sphere of activity. Motivational training is conducted as a psychology workshop or as a training within the structure of university disciplines ("Psychology", "Psychological Foundations in Advertising", "Teamwork Skills. Social Psychology", "Psychology of Management and Conflictology", "Psychology and Pedagogy of Higher Professional School", etc.).

Table 1.

The content of the training for students to increase the level of educational and professional motivation and professional self-determination

S	Goal	k
S	Determining the social network and connections of students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exercise "Sociometry": analysis of the group's social structure - Exercise "Skeptics and optimists": identifying different points of view and approaches - Exercise "Hello": communication skills and interaction - Exercise "Team name": formation of group identity - Exercise "Siamese twins": cooperation and mutual understanding
S	Determining leadership qualities and goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exercise "Invisible connection": development of empathy and mutual understanding - Exercise "Qualities of an effective manager": identification of leadership qualities - Exercise "Who am I and why": self-analysis and goal setting - Exercise "Joint account": teamwork and planning - Exercise "Goal setting": defining personal and professional goals

S	Visualization of the future and self-understanding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Exercise "Picture of the future": visualization of personal and career prospects - Exercise "Sociometry" (repetition): updating the analysis of social connections - Exercise "Fingers": self-regulation and stress resistance -Exercise "Ball": communication skills and active listening - Exercise "Sculpture through the eyes of a subordinate": empathy and understanding the perspectives of others
S		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exercise "Live obstacle": developing strategies for overcoming difficulties - Exercise "Name": formation of individual identity - Exercise "Blind and guide": trust and effective leadership - Exercise "Control parameters": time and task management
		Exercise "Physical education": physical health and stress
S	Development of creative thinking and career choice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exercise "Drawing by instruction": creative thinking and problem-solving - Exercise "Listening in different postures": active listening and empathy - Exercise "Line up!": result orientation and purposefulness - Exercise "You choose": self-determination and choice of professional path - Exercise "Hubbub": conflict and aggression management
S	Development of creativity and communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Exercise "Foreigner": communication in an unfamiliar language and adaptation - Exercise "Seating by feature": respecting diversity and developing tolerance - Exercise "Puzzle": development of creative thinking and problem-solving - Exercise "Tower of Babel": communication skills and teamwork - Exercise "Dog Harry": empathy and communication without words

S	Assessing personal growth and career plannin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exercise "A little better": assessing personal progress and achievements - Exercise "One day in the life": visualization of future professional life - Exercise "My favorite job": self-determination and choice of profession - Exercise "Postman": development of communication skills and networking - Exercise "Profession": planning steps to achieve career goals
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The program is aimed at helping students define personal and professional goals, as well as developing their social skills and communications. During the classes, students go through a series of exercises aimed at self-understanding, identifying leadership qualities, developing empathy, and managing conflicts. Particular attention is paid to the development of creativity, creative thinking, and problem-solving skills. The program also helps students manage their emotions, stress, and adapt to changes.

An important aspect is assessing personal growth and career planning. Students are provided with tools to visualize their future, determine their professional path, and develop a strategy for achieving their goals [2].

Overall, the motivational training program is a comprehensive approach to developing students as individuals and professionals, providing the necessary skills, knowledge, and confidence to successfully achieve career and personal goals. In the process of training sessions, it is important to form in students the experience of personal causality – the idea of oneself as an active subject of activity.

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